

Possible Anthelmintic Compounds. Part-IV : Synthesis of 4-(Alkoxydithiocarbonylmethyloxo) and 4-(aryl/alkyl-dithiocarbamoylmethyloxo)-3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin-3-ones

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Fourteen new derivatives of 3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazine-3-ones have been synthesised by condensing N-chloroacetyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin-3-one with either potassium-O-alkyl xanthate or ammonium-N-alkyl/aryl dithiocarbamic acid. On screening, they were found fairly active against *H. nana* in mice at dose level of 250 mg/kg.

DITHIOCARBAMATES have wide ranging physiological activity. This has been attributed to their structure, complementary to the active sites of acetylcholinesterase. It was found that some of the dithiocarbamic acid derivatives have ascericidal¹ and anthelmintic activity². Further, the presence of NH-CO-CH₂-S group was found to be responsible for anthelmintic activity in certain compounds³. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesize dithiocarbamates of 3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin-3-one with similar structural features mentioned above and to study their anthelmintic activity. The synthesis was carried out as follows :

Experimental

N-Chloroacetyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin-3-one (II) : 3,4-Dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin-3-one^{4,5} (I) (0.596 g ; 0.004 mole) was dissolved in dry benzene, NaH (200 mg) was added at room temp. and refluxed for 2 hr. Chloroacetylchloride (0.35 ml) was carefully added and it was refluxed for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was washed with water (3 × 10 ml) and the organic layer dried (sodium sulphate). After concentration, the residue was used as such without further purification, m.p. 149-50°.

4-(Alkoxydithiocarbonylmethyloxo)-3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin (III) and 4-(aryl/alkyl-dithiocarbamoylmethyloxo)-3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin-3-ones (IV) : A suspension of N-chloroacetyl-2,3-dihydro-3-ketobenzo-1,4-oxazine (II) in acetone (25 ml) was added in equimolar quantities to a solution of ammonium salt of N-substituted dithiocarbamic acid⁶ or potassium O-alkylxanthate⁶ in acetone (25 ml) and stirred at 30° for 2 hr. It was then poured into cold water. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Pharmacology :

Ten selected compounds were screened for their anthelmintic activity against *H. nana* in mice according to the method of Steward⁷.

The anthelmintic evaluation was done on the basis of mice cleared of infection and the percentage calculated. The compounds were administered orally at a dose level of 250 mg/kg of the animal.

The ALD₅₀ was carried out in mice following the method of Smith⁸ at a dose of 800 mg/kg i.p. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—4-(ALKOXYDITHIOCARBONYLMETHYLOXO)-3,4-DIHYDRO-2H-[1,4]-BENZOXAZIN-3-ONES (III) AND THEIR ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY

Sl. No.	R	Mol. formula*	m.p. °C**	Yield %	Mice survived	Mice clear from infection	% Clear	Activity
8.	-CH ₃ -	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ NO ₄ S ₂	146-48	60	5/5	2/5	40	Active
9.	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₄ S ₂	166-67	62	—	—	—	—
10.	<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₇	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO ₄ S ₂	146-47	58	—	—	—	—
11.	<i>iso</i> -C ₈ H ₇	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ NO ₄ S ₂	161-63	68	5/5	0/5	0	Inactive
12.	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₄ S ₂	138-40	65	—	—	—	—
13.	<i>iso</i> -C ₄ H ₉	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₄ S ₂	145	65	4/5	0/4	0	Inactive
14.	(CH ₂) ₂ -CH(OH) ₂ -	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ NO ₄ S ₂	165-66	50	4/5	1/4	25	Active

* All the compounds were recrystallised from methanol and gave satisfactory elemental analysis for nitrogen and sulphur.

** Melting point were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

IR absorption at 1200 to 1050 cm⁻¹ (alkylketone), absence of bands at 700-800 cm⁻¹ (C-O) provided the proof for the synthesis of the products.

TABLE 2—4-(ARYL/ALKYL-DITHIOCARBAMOYL METHYLOXO)-3,4-DIHYDRO-2H-[1,4]-BENZOXAZIN-3-ONES (IV) AND THEIR ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY

Sl. No.	R	Mol. formula*	m.p. °C**	Yield %	Mice survived	Mice clear from infection	% Clear	Activity
1.		C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	175	30	5/5	2/5	40	Active
2.		C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	145-46	20	—	—	—	—
3.	C ₆ H ₅ NH-	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	157	30	5/5	0/5	0	Inactive
4.	(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ N-	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	130	40	4/5	2/5	50	Active
5.	(CH ₂) ₂ N-	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	87-88	35	5/5	3/5	60	Active
6.	<i>p</i> '-OH-C ₆ H ₄ NH-	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	96	30	5/5	2/5	40	Active
7.	<i>o</i> '-OH-C ₆ H ₄ NH-	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S ₂	146-47	40	5/5	0/5	0	Inactive

* All the compounds were recrystallised from methanol and gave satisfactory analysis for nitrogen and sulphur.

** Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

PMR and IR data for 3,4-dihydro-2H-[1,4]-benzoxazin-3-one showed bands at 1600 (phenyl), 1690 (δ -lactam-ketone), 2900 (methylene), 3050 (enolic OH) and 3900 cm⁻¹ (NH); pmr signals at δ 4.51 (2H, s, methylene), 6.81 (4H, m, aromatic) and 10.99 (1H, b, m, NH proton) vanished on D₂O exchange.

Results and Discussion

The compounds in general were found without having any toxic manifestation as they were well tolerated upto the dose level of 800 mg/kg of the animal.

It is evident from the observations that the dithiocarbamates were capable of inhibiting the growth of the parasite. The highest activity was observed in

compound No. 8 carrying the methoxyl group. An increase in the number of methylene group had a reverse effect while replacement of alkoxy group by amines enhanced the inhibition of parasite.

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